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**Selectivity enhancement using sequential mass isolation window
acquisition with hybrid quadrupole time-of-flight mass spectrometry
for pesticide residues**

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ABSTRACT

The introduction of sequential mass isolation window acquisition mode in high-resolution quadrupole time-of-flight analysers undoubtedly represents an important improvement in the MS/MS spectra obtained when working in non-target analysis. However, the advantages and limitations of this approach have not been sufficiently defined and evaluated. The present work seeks to fill this gap by considering its application in non-target multiresidue pesticide analysis. This work focuses on the called SWATH® method, which combines both MS and MS/MS acquisition, dividing the entire mass range into smaller segments for the MS/MS mode. The effect of the number of mass isolation windows, the total cycle-time lapsed, the sensitivity obtained, the MS/MS spectra quality, the ion ratio stability as well as the identification and quantification capabilities has been evaluated. The use of ten mass isolation windows for data acquisition was selected as a compromise between the required points per chromatographic peak and the reduction in interferences achieved. An identification study was carried out on 141 pesticides in 20 vegetable matrices to check the false positives and false identifications found automatically, in accordance with the criteria set out in Document No. SANTE/11945/2015. Furthermore, special attention was given to certain issues that can make correct identification difficult, such as low fragment abundance due using of a generic collision energy, the matrix influence on the collision cell, the effect of the concentration level as well as deconvolution failure and mass window width. Finally, to verify the efficiency of the optimum parameters proposed, two proficiency samples were analysed, obtaining good results. This proved the benefits in terms of identification and quantification purposes.

Keywords: HRAMS; Pesticide residues; SWATH evaluation; Identification; Quantitation

1. Introduction

Over the last decade, the evolution of High Resolution Accurate Mass Spectrometry (HRAMS) has led to greater mass accuracy (better than 3–5 ppm) and higher resolving power (more than 25,000 at m/z 200) not to mention the instrument's increased sensitivity [1]. These developments allow us to use such a technique for trace detection within analysis while complying with the strict Maximum Residue Levels (MRLs) established by the European Union [2]. Additionally, software advances have made them more user-friendly and faster at both qualitative and quantitative purposes.

The new generation of high-resolution accurate mass spectrometers are hybrid instruments equipped with a quadrupole mass filter and a collision cell. Therefore, selectivity can be even greater when full scan is combined with MS/MS. From the full-scan, elemental composition information can be obtained (accurate mass and isotopic pattern) and from their fragmentation in MS/MS mode, information regarding the molecular structure is also achieved. These characteristics make it possible to use targeted and nontargeted acquisition modes [3], which can be either data dependent or data independent [4]. When nontargeted acquisition methods are used, the quadrupole mass filter is kept fully or partially open. If the quadrupole is fully open (the quadrupole is not filtering, only transmitting ions), all the ions formed in the ion source from the whole mass range are fragmented in the collision cell. To enhance MS/MS mode selectivity, the mass range can be divided into narrower mass isolation windows by the quadrupole and fragmented in the collision cell separately in the time. When targeted acquisition workflows are preferred, a list of precursor masses and their retention time is necessary to carry out the MS/MS experiment. For this option, narrow mass isolation windows are recommended (e.g. 1 Da). Regarding data dependent or independent acquisition mode; in the case of data dependent, the MS/MS experiment is triggered if the target precursor is present in the full-scan mode; whereas for data independent, the MS/MS fragmentation is carried out independently of the detection or absence of the precursor ion in the previous full-scan spectrum.

Recently, a new strategy has been developed for a non-target data independent acquisition workflow, called SWATH (Sequential Window Acquisition of all Theoretical fragment ion spectra) [5]. In this approach, the full-scan spectrum along the whole chromatographic run is acquired plus several MS/MS experiments in one run. The benefit of this method is that all the ions acquired from the analysed

mass range are divided into smaller segments that have optional mass window width to undergo fragmentation in the collision cell. Hence, this allows a reduction in the MS/MS spectra complexity because the number of matrix interferences is decreased, improving data quality and offering more possibilities for screening methods. Using this workflow, data processing can be carried out in two different ways: (i) extracting the precursor and fragment ion chromatograms in a similar way to that of a traditional triple quad MS/MS experiment (a target compound analysis) and (ii) using the acquired full scan and MS/MS spectra for suspect or unknown analysis. However, this latter post-acquisition workflow needs powerful post-acquisition treatment because complex MS/MS spectra are generated from multiple precursor ions. This drawback can be overcome by extracting high resolution ion chromatograms for specific fragment ions by mathematical deconvolution based on a clustering technique called Principal Components Variable Grouping (PCVG) [6]. This tool allows to separate from the MS/MS spectra the fragment ions coming from the same precursor ion and merge them to create a single spectrum that is linked to the precursor ion.

Additionally, SWATH[®] acquisition mode can be combined with target acquisition, integrating the advantages of both modalities. In the same run, it is possible to acquire data in full-scan, targeted independent MS/MS data and non-targeted independent MS/MS data acquisition. All fragments from all ions are acquired and, at the defined retention time, the fragments of the specific precursor ion are acquired. Therefore, in those time regions, the cycle time will be longer. For the pesticides with identification problems, targeted MS/MS data can be used, obtaining very high -quality MS/MS spectra. The rest of the pesticides (an unlimited number) are identified by non-targeted MS/MS data. These data can serve for non-targeted and retrospective analysis.

The SWATH[®] method has been applied to proteomics, metabolomics, toxicology and environmental monitoring [7–10]. Usually, in these areas, when using HRAMS systems without SWATH, the workflow selected is in data dependent acquisition (DDA) mode. But the main drawback of this mode lies in its biased selection criteria for precursor ions that are subjected to MS/MS fragmentation [11]. Thus, in recent years, there has been a shift towards data independent acquisition modes, where it is possible to obtain MS/MS spectra for all ionised compounds, especially when several compounds (including matrix compounds) coelute and insufficient DDA experiments are available [12]. In the case of proteomics, acquisition method optimisation was also carried out. Roemmelt et al.

did a study on the precursor mass range, mass window width and accumulation time [13]. Although most of the published SWATH-based methods typically involve constant mass isolation windows, the advantage of using variable windows has been demonstrated by Zhang et al. [14]. SWATH workflow has been applied in diverse areas; for example, it was used for proteomic quantification [13], identification and quantification of licit and illicit drugs in wastewater [8], in systematic studies of clinical and forensic toxicology [12], in herbal samples to discover their natural components [11], in migration studies on food contact material [15], etc. Regarding pesticide residue analysis, only one publication was found [16], in which two applications of this methodology were assayed at low concentration levels, one in baby foods and the other in eggs, to evaluate the presence of fipronil and its metabolites. The proposed approach provided adequate LOQs and reproducibility for routine pesticide analysis to meet the exigent MRLs set for these matrices.

The objective of the present work was to investigate the potential of SWATH[®] acquisition in a LC-ESI-QTOF-MS for the identification and quantitation of pesticide residues at low concentration levels. In addition, to evaluate its quantification performance, two Proficiency Test (PT) samples were analysed.

2. Experimental

2.1. Reagents and materials

All pesticide standards of high purity were obtained from LGC Standards (Augsburg, Germany) and Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany) and were stored at $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Individual pesticide stock solutions ($1000\text{--}2000\text{ mg L}^{-1}$) were prepared in acetonitrile and were stored in amber screw-capped glass vials in the dark at $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Standard mixed solutions and working solutions were prepared from the dilution with acetonitrile of stock solutions.

LC-MS grade methanol and ultra-gradient HPLC-grade acetonitrile were obtained from Riedel-de Haën (Selze, Germany). LC-MS optima grade water from Fisher Chemical (Fair Lawn, NJ, USA) was used. Formic acid (98% purity) was purchased from Fluka (Buchs, Switzerland). Ammonium formate was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany). Sodium citrate tribasic dihydrate, sodium chloride, sodium hydrogencitrate sesquihydrate, and anhydrous magnesium sulphate were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany).

Primary secondary amine (PSA) was obtained from Supelco (Bellefonte, PA, USA).

2.2. Sample preparation and spiking procedure

For the extraction, citrate QuEChERS method was used. An analytical portion of 10 g of sample was weighed in a 50 mL PTFE centrifuge tube. Then, 10 mL of acetonitrile were added, and the samples were shaken in an automatic axial extractor (AGYTAX®, Cirta Lab. S.L., Spain) for 4 min. Afterwards, 4 g of magnesium sulphate, 1 g of sodium chloride, 1 g of trisodium citrate dehydrate and 0.5 g of disodium hydrogencitrate sesquihydrate were added and the samples were shaken again in the automatic axial extractor for 4 min. The extract was then centrifuged at 3700 rpm for 5 min. A volume of 5 mL was transferred to a 15 mL PTFE centrifuge tube containing 750 mg of magnesium sulphate and 125 mg of PSA. The extract was shaken in a vortex for 30 s and centrifuged again (3700 rpm) for 5 min. Finally, 40 µL of 5% formic acid in acetonitrile were added to 4 mL of extract.

For the identification study, a prior analysis of the 20 samples (green pepper, peach, kiwi, onion, green celery, potato, leek, pump-kin, green beans, garlic, carrot, pineapple, zucchini, aubergine, spring onion, strawberry, broccoli, lemon, cauliflower, and cabbage) was performed in order to ensure that they did not contain any of the target compounds. Then, the extracts were spiked at 0.010 and 0.100 mg/kg. For that purpose, 50 µL of the QuEChERS extract were evaporated to dryness with a nitrogen stream and reconstituted with 50 µL of the appropriate concentration of the working solution and 200 µL of water. To control the injection process, 10 µL of dimethoate-d₆ (injection standard) at 2.5 mg/L was added to all the vials injected. The extract was 5 times diluted prior the injection so, the final samples contained 0.2 g of sample per mL. All concentration values which appear in the paper refer to the concentration in the matrix before dilution.

2.3. LC-HRAMS analysis

For the liquid chromatography separation, Exion LC (Sciex, Massachusetts, USA) was used. Mobile phase A was 98% water and 2% methanol whereas mobile phase B was 98% methanol and 2% water; both mobile phases contained 5 mM of ammonium formate and 0.1% formic acid. Separation was carried out on a Zorbax Eclipse Plus C8 column (Agilent, Santa Clara, USA). The length, diameter and particle size were 100 mm, 2.1 mm and 1.8 µm, respectively. The column was thermostated at 35 °C.

The mobile phase gradient started from 80% of mobile phase A and was maintained for 2 min, from 2 to 15 min the amount of mobile phase B increased linearly to 100% and this proportion was maintained for another 2 min. Following this, the mobile phase was changed to 80% A and maintained over 3 min for re-equilibration, being the total run time 20 min. The injection volume was 5 μ L. The autosampler was thermostated at 10 ° C.

A X500R QTOF-MS (Sciex, Massachusetts, USA) equipped with Turbo VTM Source with Twin Sprayer probe for electrospray ionisation was used for acquisition. The source parameters in positive polarity were as follows: Ion source gas 1: 40 psi; Ion source gas 2: 50 psi; Curtain gas: 25 psi; CAD gas: 7 psi; Temperature: 350 ° C; Spray voltage: 5500 V. Resolution power of the TOF system was 32,000 FWHM (for m/z 200). SWATH[®], a data independent non-target acquisition mode was used. Parameters used in full scan mode were: Accumulation time: 0.2 s; Declustering potential: 80 V; TOF start mass: 100; TOF stop mass: 950. For the MS/MS mode the parameters were: Accumulation time: 0.05 s; TOF start mass: 50; TOF stop mass: 950. A generic collision energy spread of 35 ± 15 V was used. The number of mass isolation windows in Q1 was set as 10, divided as follows: m/z 100–185, 184–270, 269–355, 354–440, 439–525, 524–610, 609–695, 694–780, 779–865 and 864–950. A total cycle time of 0.78 s was obtained.

An external TOF mass calibration was carried out daily. For the calibration, a mixture containing 10 compounds with masses in the range of 132.9049–2034.6255 amu was used. Also, this mixture was automatically injected along the batch every 5 samples to maintain the mass accuracy below 2 ppm. SciexOS software v. 1.3 (Sciex, Massachusetts, USA) was used for data acquisition, qualitative and quantitative analyses.

2.4. Evaluation of the number and width of mass isolation windows

Various tests were carried out with 5 matrices (green pepper, carrot, lemon, broccoli and leek), spiked at different concentration levels (0.010 and 0.050 mg/kg) of the selected pesticides using different number of mass isolation windows (1, 5, 10 and 20 windows). The accumulation time in full-scan and in MS/MS mode is maintained in all workflows at 200 and 50 ms, respectively. Therefore, the total cycle time increases with the number of mass isolation windows. The MS/MS spectrum quality, number of points per chromatographic peak (ppp) and the stability of the ion ratio were evaluated in this study to select the best compromise

situation.

When the number of mass isolation windows was optimised, their mass window width was also assessed. In this case, variable mass window widths were used instead of applying in all the mass isolation windows the same range. The total cycle time is the same in all the experiments, only the mass range filtered by the quadrupole to perform the MS/MS fragmentation of the ions vary to change the selectivity of the MS/MS spectrum.

2.5. Identification study

A false positive and false identification study was carried out by injecting 20 blank samples and spiked samples, at 0.010 and 0.100 mg/kg, by using the SWATH method with 10 mass isolation windows. A total of 141 LC amenable compounds from the multi-annual control program list [17] were evaluated in this study.

The identification criteria followed were those set out at the SANTE Document [18]: retention time \pm 0.1 min from the standard, detection of two ions (precursor plus one fragment ion) with signal-to-noise ratio higher than 3, mass accuracy equal or lower than 5 ppm if the m/z is higher than 200 (if lower, mass accuracy equal or below 1 m Da), and ion ratio (fragment ion area/precursor ion area) within \pm 30% of the average of the calibration standard from the same sequence. A mass window extraction width of 5 ppm was used in this study. This was a compromise situation in order to limit the risk of false identifications in quantitative analysis [19].

Additionally, a suspect screening was performed to a zucchini sample spiked at 0.010 mg/kg injected with the 5 and 10 mass isolation window approaches. The purpose of this experiment was to check the efficacy of the deconvolution carried out to align the fragments to their corresponding precursor ion. An in-house accurate MS/MS spectral library including 117 of the spiked compounds was used to identify automatically the analytes. This library contains the exact mass of the precursor ion, the MS/MS spectrum with accurate mass and analytes's retention time. Precursor ion exact mass was obtained automatically from the software by introducing the molecular formula; retention time and fragment ion accurate mass was obtained experimentally by injection of the analytical standard in the system. The most abundant fragment ion was chosen for this study. The list of masses and retention time for each pair of precursor ion/fragment ion are showed in Table S1 (supplemental material).

2.6. Combination of target and non-target acquisition mode

The combination of target and non-target acquisition in the same run combines advantages and eliminates some inconveniences of both types of acquisition [4]. In this procedure, SWATH with 10 mass isolation windows with the same mass range in each window plus target acquisition for two compounds with a low fragment ion (hexaconazole and myclobutanil) was used. Comparison of the results in target and non-target mode was performed.

2.7. Application of the method

To evaluate the applicability of the proposed method and its quantitation performance, two PT samples were analysed by using the optimised SWATH acquisition method. The samples were the EUPT-FV20 (multiresidue pesticide analysis in lemon) and the FAPAS 2017 pesticide residues in pear purée.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Evaluation of the number of mass isolation windows

As a first step in the evaluation of this acquisition mode, an assessment of the number of mass isolation windows using equal mass window width in each experiment was performed. Several tests were carried out using 1, 5, 10 and 20 mass isolation windows over the entire m/z range (100–950). The obtained mass window widths were 850, 170, 85 and 43 Da in each window, respectively.

The parameters to compare the methods used were the number of points per peak (linked to the total cycle time), the sensitivity obtained, the quality of the MS/MS mode, and the ion ratio stability.

3.1.1. Number of points per peak

The number of points per peak acquired has a direct influence on the reproducibility of the analyte's peak area. By increasing the number of mass isolation windows, the total cycle time is extended. The cycle times obtained when applying the different methods were: 0.31 s, 0.52 s, 0.78 s and 1.32 s (for the 1, 5, 10 and 20 mass isolation window methods, respectively). This lengthening in the cycle time means that the acquired points per peak (ppp) decrease. Therefore, this

may affect chromatographic peak reproducibility.

As can be seen in Fig. 1, the points acquired for the precursor ion decreased from 23 to 9. These ppp values are still enough to obtain good area reproducibility. Using the leek example (considered a “difficult” matrix because of its high coextractives content), peak response repeatability was measured by 5 injections from the same vial and was represented as the relative standard deviation (RSD, %). With the 1 and 5 mass isolation window methods, 90% of the compounds had RSD values below 15%. The number of compounds increased to 92% with the 10 mass isolation window method but decreased to 85% with the 20 window method. The results were similar for the rest of the studied matrices at both concentration levels (0.010 and 0.100 mg/kg).

3.1.2. Sensitivity

As the cycle time increases along with the number of mass isolation windows, it is supposed that analytes sensitivity will decrease, because less ppp are acquired [12]. This was observed for the precursor ions in the same matrix in at least 90.9% of the compounds. If the precursor ion response was compared between the methods, it showed a decrease when increasing the number of windows. Nevertheless, important improvements in sensitivity were observed for fragment ions when the entire mass range was divided into 10 mass isolation windows.

Fig. 2 shows the chromatograms for the precursor ion and the fragment ion of acetamiprid at 0.010 mg/kg in carrot and lemon. The fragment ion area increased 7–9 many times when moving from 5 to 10 mass isolation windows. If the number of windows increased to 20, the sensitivity of the MS/MS experiment slightly decreased. Hence, in accordance with the SANTE AQC Document, which established that two ions are necessary for compound identification, an improvement in the fragment ion intensity will allow the identification limits to be reduced.

3.1.3. Spectral quality of the MS/MS mode

The quality of the MS/MS spectrum depends on the scan time set to acquire the required mass range. If the number of ions reaching the multichannel plate is high in the same scan time, the quality of the MS/MS spectrum is lower. The MS/MS accumulation time optimum for this study was set at 50 ms. With lower accumulation time, the selected fragment ions are barely seen because the noise is high, and with longer accumulation times, the number of points per peaks acquired can be compromised. If the quadrupole is fully open (1 mass isolation window), all

the ions from the ionisation source reach the collision cell where they are fragmented; therefore, the MS/MS spectrum contains a large amount of fragment ions from coeluting matrix components that might be a source of false positive or false identifications as well as increasing the spectral noise level. When using mass isolation windows, the entire mass range analysed is divided into different time segments by Q1, before performing the MS/MS fragmentation step, so less ions arrive at the collision cell in the same time segment. This is an effective way to improve selectivity in MS/MS mode. Taking the identification of fluopyram at 0.010 mg/kg in leek as an example, Fig. 3(a–d) shows how the specificity and the spectral quality of the MS/MS mode in SWATH acquisition can be improved using a higher number of narrower mass isolation windows. With 1 mass isolation window, the selected fragments of fluopyram (m/z 397.0537) showed an ion ratio (fragment/precursor ion) deviation above 30% for both fragment ions (Fig. 3a) and the signal-to-noise ratio for the fragment ions was high (almost half of the ion intensity). Consequently, one mass isolation window was not enough to adequately determine the analyte fragment ions from the matrix ions. If 5 or 10 mass isolation windows are used, the entire mass range is divided into a mass isolation window of 170 and 85 Da, respectively, and the number of possible interferences in the MS/MS spectrum is smaller. In Fig. 3b and c, the intensity of the fragment ions is higher than with just one mass isolation window and the noise is lower, hence, the MS/MS spectrum quality is higher and the ion ratio criteria is met. In the same way, by increasing the number of mass isolation windows to 20, a cleaner MS/MS spectrum is produced and an improved signal-to-noise ratio can be observed. However, this resulted in a longer acquisition cycle time, the number of ppp was lower and, consequently, the ion ratio criteria failed for one of the ions (Fig. 3d).

3.1.4. Stability of the ion ratio

The ion ratio obtained from the precursor ion area vs. the fragment ion area is a critical parameter for correct identification when considering potential isobaric compounds and a large scope of analytes. Therefore, its stability (or small variation range) across different concentrations and matrices is highly desirable.

An evaluation was carried out of the cases above a critical value (established as a difference within $\pm 30\%$ of the standards' average area) with a different number of mass isolation windows; this was done by analysing 5 matrices (green pepper, carrot, lemon, broccoli and leek) spiked at 0.010 and 0.050 mg/kg. Taking only the automatic results from the software into account, in general, the number of cases

above the critical value decreased as the number of mass isolation windows increased. In total, 705 possible results can be obtained by studying 5 matrices and 141 compounds. Table 1 shows the number of cases above the critical value at both concentration levels that were acquired with 1, 5, 10 and 20 mass isolation windows. The largest number of cases corresponded to the 0.010 mg/kg concentration level when acquiring the data with 1 mass isolation window (11.3%). When the concentration level increased, this figure decreased to 6.4% because the fragment ion was more intense, more ppp were acquired and the ion ratio variation was smaller. The lowest value was found at 0.050 mg/kg when applying the 10 mass isolation windows method (0.6% of cases). Most of the results were obtained in leek and broccoli (54% of the study results). The two further cases above $\pm 30\%$ acquired with 20 mass isolation windows were due to the low intensity of those analytes and the low number of ppp acquired for them, making their result variability higher. This is caused by the combination of a longer cycle time for this approach and the complexity of the matrices, with their strong matrix effects and signal suppression of the ions. These two characteristics hinder the acquisition of sufficient ppp, hampering the ion ratio within the criterion. Another reason might be the matrix influence at the collision cell. The wider the mass isolation window, the higher the number of coextractive compounds from the matrix at the collision cell in the MS/MS mode; this varies the compound's fragmentation abundance pattern making it difficult to fulfil the ion ratio criteria. This phenomenon can be observed especially in broccoli and leek (two of the complex matrices evaluated). In these matrices, the number of non identified compounds at 0.010 mg/kg decreased when the number of mass isolation windows increased (12-8-7-6 and 16-12-8-7 with 1, 5, 10, and 20 mass isolation windows in broccoli and leek, respectively). Another way of looking at this is to focus on one compound (flufenoxuron, Fig. 4). When using 1 mass isolation window, the ion ratio for flufenoxuron in three matrices (carrot, broccoli and lemon) at the two concentration levels varied by 65%. On the other hand, if 10 mass isolation windows were used, the ion ratio difference was only 18%. In the latter case, because of the high ion ratio stability, it was possible to identify flufenoxuron in any of the matrices independently of the matrix used to prepare the calibration curve. Consequently, in some cases, a significant ion ratio variation can be overcome by reducing the mass window width.

3.1.5. Acquisition method selection

In view of the results, and as a compromise for those aspects mentioned above (chromatographic peak reproducibility, MS/MS spectrum quality, sensitivity and ion ratio stability), 10 mass isolation windows (85 Da for each window) were chosen as being the optimum number for completing the study. With this method, the ranges used for ion isolation in Q1, prior to MS/MS fragmentation, was narrow enough to reduce the maximum number of interferences, allowing to fulfil the identification criteria automatically and maintaining good sensitivity and reproducibility of the peak area.

3.2. Identification study

Once the method was set, the 20 blank extracts of the selected matrices were injected. Their extracts spiked with 141 pesticides at two concentration levels were also analysed, allowing to evaluate the number of false positives and false identifications. A false identification is considered to be a detection in which the SANTE AQC Document identification criteria are not met (an ion ratio \pm 30% outside of the standard or a mass error above 5 ppm).

No false positives were found if the retention time and one ion of the analyte were searched for. Regarding the non identified compounds, a range from 0 to 18.3% was found at 0.010 mg/kg; with an average of 1.3%. At 0.100 mg/kg, the non identified compounds were between 0 and 3.5% of the total number of possible results; the average being 0.1% (Table 2). It is important to note that approximately 65% of all the false identifications observed in this study were found in broccoli, onion, spring onion, garlic and leek (some of the complex matrices selected for this study). This means, there was a significant matrix interference effect from the coextractive compounds, making it difficult to identify the compounds.

In some cases, the reasons the compounds were not identified were because they did not fulfil the ion ratio criterion, the compound was not detected at all or one of the ions had a mass error above 5 ppm (Table 2). This can be due to matrix suppression or due to a matrix interference that shifts one ion's accurate mass, or because the fragment ion intensity is low on account of using a generic collision energy during the fragmentation step in the MS/MS mode, or even because of the large number of ions in the MS/MS fragmentation process. Generally speaking, more non identified compounds are observed because of ion ratio non-compliance

(Table 2) than for other reasons. Therefore, by reviewing the data manually, these percentages can be significantly reduced.

With regard to suspect screening, 100% of the spiked analytes present in the library were automatically identified in the zucchini sample; acquired using SWATH with 10 mass isolation windows. If we changed to SWATH with 5 mass isolation windows, the value dropped to 90%, and to 68% with 1 window. An example of this can be seen in Fig. 5, where propaquizafop was automatically detected when applying the 10 mass isolation windows (but not with 5). The precursor ion sensitivity was even higher using 5 windows, but the MS/MS spectrum quality was lower (m/z 299.0591 is in the same noise range) so the library spectrum fit was low. This can be explained because with 5 mass isolation windows, more matrix ions are fragmented at the same time in the collision cell so the variability in ion intensity can be greater. Furthermore, the variability in the fragment's peak shape might also be higher compared to the precursor's peak shape; thus, the deconvolution performed to align the precursor ion with its fragment ions might fail. Consequently, some fragments cannot be associated to their precursor ions, and the identification is unsuccessful.

3.3. Use of mass isolation windows with variable width

To carry out the suitability study of the SWATH acquisition method for pesticide analysis, all the experiments used the same mass range in all the windows. It is potentially a good approach to reduce the mass range in the windows where more matrix compounds might interfere with the analytes, this improves the selectivity without increasing the cycle time [14]. For this reason, an experiment using SWATH with 10 mass isolation windows was carried out with the following mass ranges: 100–200, 199–240, 239–280, 279–320, 319–360, 359–400, 390–440, 439–480, 479–520 and 519–950 amu. This means the method comprised a first window of 100 amu (around the lowest masses), 8 windows of 40 amu and, finally, a large window of 430 amu; the cycle time was 0.78 s.

Using this method, some of the drawbacks seen in the previous section were remedied, especially those resulting from a high mass error or ion ratio outside the 30% range caused by matrix interference. As an example, in broccoli, it was not possible to identify fenhexamid using 10 fixed mass isolation windows at 0.010 mg/kg (Fig. 6). Even with a mass error below 5 ppm in both ions, the ion ratio was 4-times higher at this concentration level than at 0.050 mg/kg. After careful

investigation of the blank extract, a huge fragment ion peak was observed, with a mass error of 7.7 ppm. By applying the 10 mass isolation windows method with a different mass window width, the fragment ion peak obtained for fenhexamid in the blank sample was almost at the same level as the noise region, and the ion ratio deviation was within 23%. Using different mass ranges avoids the need for manual investigation, speeding up the data treatment process. These results are in accordance with those obtained by Zhang et al. [14], in which they found that narrower mass isolation windows improved the selectivity of the targeted analytes without compromising any other instrument parameters such as the cycle time.

3.4. Combination of target and non-target acquisition mode

Of the 141 compounds studied, there were two compounds with very low fragment ions (hexaconazole and myclobuthanil). To try to overcome this disadvantage, which might be due to using a generic collision energy or because of interference from matrix compounds during the MS/MS fragmentation process, a method combining non-target and target acquisition modes for these compounds was used. Throughout the run, the cycle time was 0.2 s longer and, at the retention time of the two compounds for which the target analysis was fired, the cycle time was extended by 0.05 s. On the other hand, the quadrupole filtered the precursor ion for these compounds with a mass window width of 0.7 Da and their optimum collision energy could be applied. Hence, the fragment ion intensity was higher. This approach is a good option when the laboratory scope includes very few compounds with low MS/MS fragmentation.

For hexaconazole, in broccoli at 0.010 mg/kg, the mass error of the fragment ion (m/z 158.9767) was 429 ppm in non-target mode because the ion was very low (almost noise) whereas in target mode, the mass error was -2.7 ppm, the ion ratio difference being within $\pm 30\%$. Therefore, this compound can be automatically identified using the target mode. In the case of myclobuthanil, the mass error in non-target mode was 6.1 ppm (a value above that recommended for identification). In target mode, the mass error was 4.2 ppm and the ion ratio criteria were met again. Accordingly, potential non identification of these two compounds was avoided using this approach.

3.5. Application of the method

To prove the effectiveness of the developed method and its suitability in quantitative analysis, it was applied to two proficiency test samples (EUPT-FV20 – lemon, and FAPAS 2017 – pear). The corresponding results are showed in [Table 3](#). The concentration obtained from applying matrix match-calibration was very close to the assigned value for each pesticide present in the PT samples. Z score values were always equal or below 1.1, meaning that acceptable results were obtained for the entire range of concentration levels present (0.022 – 0.483 mg/kg). No false positives or false identifications were detected in either of the samples. The quantitative data were in good agreement, thus demonstrating good quantitation capabilities.

4. Conclusions

Combining MS and MS/MS modes using sequential mass isolation windows clearly offers important advantages for improving identification and quantitation in LC-ESI-QTOF-MS. The SWATH[®] mode is a very robust and effective workflow allowing the easy selection of fixed or variable mass window widths depending on the compounds of interest.

Narrowing the mass isolation window (e.g. to 20 Da) improves the selectivity and the sensitivity in MS/MS mode because less matrix interferences arrive at the collision cell at the same time as the analytes, and the deconvolution algorithm works more efficiently. The number of ions arriving at the collision cell can interfere with the fragmentation process, which might alter the intensity and the ion-ratio abundance in different matrices. Using 10 mass isolation windows under the conditions studied (85 Da) was enough for the proper identification of a wide scope of pesticide residues. The ion ratio stability was good (close to 100% of cases) allowing its use for identification purposes. It was only in complex matrices that there were a certain number of ion ratios outside the 30% variability (9.2%), in general, it was $\leq 2.5\%$ at the 0.010 mg/kg level. The number of points per peak obtained with 10 mass isolation windows was enough for good area reproducibility. Furthermore, applying LC-ESI-QTOF-MS/MS as a quantitative technique in food analysis demonstrated good accuracy in all the cases studied, even at a low concentration level (0.010 mg/kg).

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest with any of the instruments or materials referred to in this work.

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Fig. 1. Points per peak (ppp) of the extracted ion chromatogram (XIC) for ethoprophos (m/z 243.0637) at 0.010 mg/kg in leek, obtained using the four SWATH methods tested: a) 1 mass isolation window; b) 5 mass isolation windows; c) 10 mass isolation windows; and d) 20 mass isolation windows.

Fig. 2. Intensity of the peaks for acetamiprid at 0.010 mg/kg in a) carrot and b) lemon. In pink, the precursor ion peak (m/z 223.0745) and in blue, the fragment ion peak (m/z 126.0097) (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article).

Fig. 3. Identification of fluopyram (m/z 397.0537) at 0.010 mg/kg in leek employing a) 1 mass isolation window from 50 to 950 Da; b) 5 mass isolation windows selecting the window 349–520 Da; c) 10 mass isolation windows, extracting the ion from the 354–440 Da window, and d) 20 mass isolation windows, from window 396–440 Da. On the left side, the precursor ion XIC in MS mode; in the centre, the fragment ion XIC (C₈ H₄ F₃ O, m/z 173.0209) and on the right side, the MS/MS spectrum.

Fig. 4. Ion ratios for the chromatographic peaks of flufenoxuron (m/z 489.0435) in three matrices (carrot, broccoli and lemon) at two concentration levels acquired with a) 1 mass isolation window and b) 10 mass isolation windows.

Fig. 5. The XIC, MS/MS spectrum and automatic library search for propaquizafop (m/z 444.1321) in zucchini spiked at 0.010 mg/kg. a) The sample acquired with 5 mass isolation windows and b) the sample acquired with 10 mass isolation windows.

Fig. 6. Fenhexamid in broccoli in a blank sample, at 0.010 mg/kg and 0.050 mg/kg acquired with a) 10 fixed mass isolation windows (85 Da) and b) 10 variable mass isolation windows ($100 \times 1-40 \times 8-430 \times 1$ Da). In pink, the precursor ion, m/z 302.0709; in blue, the fragment ion, m/z 97.1005. The ion ratio deviation refers to the difference between the ion ratios at 0.010 and 0.050 mg/kg (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article).

Table 1. Number of compounds with ion ratios above 30%, obtained in 5 matrices spiked with 141 pesticides using different mass isolation windows. The matrices in which the majority of the results were obtained are highlighted along with the percentage of cases obtained from the total of cases above the critical value.

Acquisition method	Total # (%)		Matrices with higher number of results
	0.010 mg/kg	0.050 mg/kg	
1 mass isolation window	80 (11.3%)	45 (6.4%)	Leek and Broccoli (44%)
5 mass isolation windows	23 (3.3%)	9 (1.3 %)	Leek and Broccoli (50%)
10 mass isolation windows	23 (3.3%)	4 (0.6 %)	Leek and Broccoli (60%)
20 mass isolation windows	25 (3.5%)	5 (0.7 %)	Leek and Broccoli (62%)

Table 2. Percentage of total results not identified (ion ratio failed, mass error > 5 ppm or not detected) obtained using the SWATH method with 10 mass isolation windows (85 Da per window) in the twenty matrices selected at the two concentration levels studied. Total number of compounds: 141.

0.010 mg/kg	Green Pepper	Peach	Potato	Zucchini	Pumpkin	Green Beans	Pineapple	Raspberry	Aubergine	Carrot	Broccoli	Cauliflower	Cabbage	Kiwi	Lemon	Green Celery	Onion	Spring Onion	Garlic	Leek
Ion ratio outside 30%	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.7	1.4	2.8	1.4	0.7	1.4	2.1	5.6	1.4	2.1	0.7	2.8	1.4	2.1	3.5	9.2	5.6
Mass error > 5 ppm*	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.4	1.4	2.1	1.4	0.0	2.1	1.4	2.8	4.2	7.0	3.5
No detected*	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.7	2.1	0.7
0.100 mg/kg	Green Pepper	Peach	Potato	Zucchini	Pumpkin	Green Beans	Pineapple	Raspberry	Aubergine	Carrot	Broccoli	Cauliflower	Cabbage	Kiwi	Lemon	Green Celery	Onion	Spring Onion	Garlic	Leek
Ion ratio outside 30%	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.8	1.4
Mass error > 5 ppm*	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.0
No detected*	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

* Those results are obtained due to the complexity of the matrices (matrix interference effect).

Table 3. Results obtained using the 10 mass isolation windows method for two PT samples; one in lemon (EUPT-FV 19) and one in pear (FAPAS 2017).

EUPT-FV 19			
	Concentration (mg/kg)	Assigned value (mg/kg)	Z Score
Boscalid	0.483	0.381	1.1
Carbendazim	0.144	0.135	0.3
Chlorantraniliprole	0.216	0.185	0.7
Chlorpyrifos	0.141	0.131	0.3
Diazinon	0.208	0.167	1.0
Ethoprophos	0.043	0.038	0.5
Fluopyram	0.154	0.129	0.8
Imidacloprid	0.185	0.158	0.7
Omethoate	0.022	0.021	0.2
Propamocarb	0.150	0.125	0.8
Pyraclostrobin	0.143	0.185	-0.9
FAPAS			
	Concentration (mg/kg)	Assigned value (mg/kg)	Z Score
Chlorantoaniliprole	0.146	0.120	-0.9
Diniconazole	0.043	0.032	-1.4
Fluquinazole	0.169	0.132	-1.1
Pyraclostrobin	0.107	0.083	-1.2
Teflubenzuron	0.226	0.155	-1.8

Supplemental Material

Table S1. Processing parameter for the evaluation of the SWATH method and the identification study.

Compound name	Formula	Adduct	Precursor ion m/z	Fragment Ion m/z	Retention time (min)	Experiment index
Acephate	C4H10NO3PS	[M+H] ⁺	184.01918	142.9928	1.53	2 +TOF MSMS [100 - 185] (50 - 950)
Acetamiprid	C10H11ClN4	[M+H] ⁺	223.0745	126.0097	6.26	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Azinphos-methyl	C10H12N3O3PS2	[M+H] ⁺	318.01305	132.0443	10.88	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Azoxystrobin	C22H17N3O5	[M+H] ⁺	404.1241	372.0968	11.26	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Bifenazate	C17H20N2O3	[M+H] ⁺	301.15467	170.0961	12.05	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Boscalid	C18H12Cl2N2O	[M+H] ⁺	343.03994	307.0636	11.56	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Bromuconazole	C13H12BrCl2N3O	[M+H] ⁺	375.96136	158.9763	11.95 + 12.73	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Bupirimate	C13H24N4O3S	[M+H] ⁺	317.16419	166.0969	12.25	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Buprofezin	C16H23N3O5	[M+H] ⁺	306.16346	106.0643	14.14	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Carbaryl	C12H11NO2	[M+H] ⁺	202.08626	127.0536	9.55	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Carbendazim	C9H9N3O2	[M+H] ⁺	192.07675	160.0495	3.2	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Chlorantraniliprole	C18H14BrCl2N5O2	[M+H] ⁺	481.97807	283.9226	10.95	6 +TOF MSMS [439 - 525] (50 - 950)
Chlorfenvinphos	C12H14Cl3O4P	[M+H] ⁺	358.97681	204.9377	13.16	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Chlorpyrifos	C9H11Cl3NO3PS	[M+H] ⁺	349.93356	197.9275	14.29	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Chlorpyrifos-methyl	C7H7Cl3NO3PS	[M+H] ⁺	321.90226	289.8758	13.37	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Clofentezine	C14H8Cl2N4	[M+H] ⁺	303.01988	138.0103	13	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Clomazone	C12H14ClNO2	[M+H] ⁺	240.07858	125.0151	11.06	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Coumaphos	C14H16ClO5PS	[M+H] ⁺	363.02174	226.9934	12.87	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Cyazofamid	C13H13ClN4O2S	[M+H] ⁺	325.05205	108.0104	12.41	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Cyprodinil	C14H15N3	[M+H] ⁺	226.13387	210.1033	12.18	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Demeton-S-Methyl-Sulfone	C6H15O5PS2	[M+H] ⁺	263.01713	169.0084	3.75	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Demeton-S-methylsulfoxide	C6H15O4PS2	[M+H] ⁺	247.02221	109.0051	3.19	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Diazinon	C12H21N2O3PS	[M+H] ⁺	305.10833	169.079	13.09	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Dichlorvos	C4H7Cl2O4P	[M+H] ⁺	220.95318	109.0052	9.04	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)

Compound name	Formula	Adduct	Precursor ion m/z	Fragment ion m/z	Retention time (min)	Experiment index
Dicrotophos	C8H16NO5P	[M+H] ⁺	238.08389	112.0756	5.13	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Diethofencarb	C14H21NO4	[M+H] ⁺	268.15433	124.0392	11.19	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Difenoconazole	C19H17Cl2N3O3	[M+H] ⁺	406.07197	251.0028	13.38	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Diflubenzuron	C14H9ClF2N2O2	[M+H] ⁺	311.03934	141.0147	12.47	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Dimethoate	C5H12NO3PS2	[M+H] ⁺	230.0069	124.9813	6.21	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Dimethomorph	C21H22ClNO4	[M+H] ⁺	388.13101	301.0626	11.72	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Diuron	C9H10Cl2N2O	[M+H] ⁺	233.02429	72.0442	10.62	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Emamectin B1a	C49H75NO13	[M+H] ⁺	886.53112	158.1178	13.88	11 +TOF MSMS [864 - 950] (50 - 950)
Epoxiconazole	C17H13ClFN3O	[M+H] ⁺	330.08039	121.0444	12.31	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Ethion	C9H22O4P2S4	[M+H] ⁺	384.99489	142.9381	14.3	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Ethirimol	C11H19N3O	[M+H] ⁺	210.16009	140.107	7.74	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Ethoprophos	C8H19O2PS2	[M+H] ⁺	243.06369	130.9377	12.43	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Etofenprox	C25H28O3	[M+NH4] ⁺	394.23767	177.1274	15.46	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Fenamidone	C17H17N3OS	[M+H] ⁺	312.11651	92.049	11.56	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Fenamiphos	C13H22NO3PS	[M+H] ⁺	304.11308	217.0079	12.64	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Fenamiphos-sulfone	C13H22NO5PS	[M+H] ⁺	336.10291	266.0242	9.57	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Fenamiphos-sulfoxide	C13H22NO4PS	[M+H] ⁺	320.10799	233.0034	9.34	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Fenarimol	C17H12Cl2N2O	[M+H] ⁺	331.03994	268.0523	12.31	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Fenazaquin	C20H22N2O	[M+H] ⁺	307.18049	161.1323	14.86	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Fenbuconazole	C19H17ClN4	[M+H] ⁺	337.12145	125.0151	12.47	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Fenhexamid	C14H17Cl2NO2	[M+H] ⁺	302.07091	97.1005	12.22	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Fenoxycarb	C17H19NO4	[M+H] ⁺	302.13868	88.0385	12.6	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Fenpropathrin	C22H23NO3	[M+H] ⁺	350.17507	125.095	14.85	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Fenpropimorph	C20H33NO	[M+H] ⁺	304.26349	147.1161	11.14	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Fenpyrazamine	C17H21N3O2S	[M+H] ⁺	332.14272	230.1279	12.05	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Fenpyroximate	C24H27N3O4	[M+H] ⁺	422.20743	366.1449	14.72	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)

Compound name	Formula	Adduct	Precursor ion m/z	Fragment ion m/z	Retention time (min)	Experiment index
Fenthion	C10H15O3PS2	[M+H] ⁺	279.0273	169.0135	12.83	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Fenthion-sulfone	C10H15O5PS2	[M+H] ⁺	311.01713	124.9817	9.81	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Fenthion-sulfoxide	C10H15O4PS2	[M+H] ⁺	295.02221	279.9981	9.49	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Flonicamid	C9H6F3N3O	[M+H] ⁺	230.05357	203.0426	3.75	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Flufenacet	C14H13F4N3O2S	[M+H] ⁺	364.07374	152.0506	12.43	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Flufenoxuron	C21H11ClF6N2O3	[M+H] ⁺	489.04352	158.0409	14.54	6 +TOF MSMS [439 - 525] (50 - 950)
Fluopyram	C16H11ClF6N2O	[M+H] ⁺	397.05369	173.0209	12.29	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Fluquinconazole	C16H8Cl2FN5O	[M+H] ⁺	376.01627	306.9847	12.04	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Flusilazole	C16H15F2N3Si	[M+H] ⁺	316.10761	165.0699	12.67	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Flutriafol	C16H13F2N3O	[M+H] ⁺	302.10994	70.0396	10.43	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Formetanate	C11H15N3O2	[M+H] ⁺	222.1237	165.1021	1.39	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Fosthiazate	C9H18NO3PS2	[M+H] ⁺	284.05385	104.0162	10.03	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Haloxyfop	C15H11ClF3NO4	[M+H] ⁺	362.04015	316.0347	12.75	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Hexaconazole	C14H17Cl2N3O	[M+H] ⁺	314.08214	158.9767	13.28	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Hexythiazox	C17H21ClN2O2S	[M+H] ⁺	353.1085	168.0574	14.48	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Imazalil	C14H14Cl2N2O	[M+H] ⁺	297.05559	158.9764	10	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Imidacloprid	C9H10ClN5O2	[M+H] ⁺	256.05958	209.0589	5.24	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Indoxacarb	C22H17ClF3N3O7	[M+H] ⁺	528.07799	218.0426	13.62	7 +TOF MSMS [524 - 610] (50 - 950)
Iprovalicarb	C18H28N2O3	[M+H] ⁺	321.21727	119.085	12.38	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Isocarbophos	C11H16NO4PS	[M+Na] ⁺	312.04299	230.9875	10.65	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Isoprocarb	C11H15NO2	[M+H] ⁺	194.11756	95.0491	10.42	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Isoxaflutole	C15H12F3NO4S	[M+H] ⁺	360.05119	250.9987	10.7	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Kresoxim-methyl	C18H19NO4	[M+H] ⁺	314.13868	131.0729	12.76	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Linuron	C9H10Cl2N2O2	[M+H] ⁺	249.01921	159.9719	11.3	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Malathion	C10H19O6PS2	[M+H] ⁺	331.04334	124.9823	11.84	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Mandipropamid	C23H22ClNO4	[M+H] ⁺	412.13101	328.1094	11.67	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)

Compound name	Formula	Adduct	Precursor ion m/z	Fragment ion m/z	Retention time (min)	Experiment index
Mepanipyrim	C14H13N3	[M+H] ⁺	224.11822	106.0652	11.9	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Metalaxyl	C15H21NO4	[M+H] ⁺	280.15433	160.1117	10.62	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Metconazole	C17H22ClN3O	[M+H] ⁺	320.15242	125.0148	13.22	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Methidathion	C6H11N2O4PS3	[M+H] ⁺	302.96913	85.0394	10.8	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Methiocarb	C11H15NO2S	[M+H] ⁺	226.08963	121.0646	11.48	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Methiocarb-sulfoxide	C11H15NO3S	[M+H] ⁺	242.08454	170.0396	5.88	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Methoxyfenozide	C22H28N2O3	[M+H] ⁺	369.21727	149.0591	12.08	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Metobromuron	C9H11BrN2O2	[M+H] ⁺	259.00767	169.9608	10.09	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Monocrotophos	C7H14NO5P	[M+H] ⁺	224.06824	127.0152	4.36	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Myclobutanil	C15H17ClN4	[M+H] ⁺	289.12145	125.0147	12.03	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Nitenpyram	C11H15ClN4O2	[M+H] ⁺	271.09563	126.0106	2.65	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Omethoate	C5H12NO4PS	[M+H] ⁺	214.02974	124.9818	1.77	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Oxadixyl	C14H18N2O4	[M+H] ⁺	279.13393	132.0809	8.37	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Paclobutrazol	C15H20ClN3O	[M+H] ⁺	294.13677	70.0396	11.85	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Paraoxon methyl	C8H10NO6P	[M+H] ⁺	248.03185	202.0389	8.13	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Penconazole	C13H15Cl2N3	[M+H] ⁺	284.07158	158.9761	12.97	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Pencycuron	C19H21ClN2O	[M+H] ⁺	329.14152	125.0144	13.48	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Pendimethalin	C13H19N3O4	[M+H] ⁺	282.14483	212.0663	14.4	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Phenthoate	C12H17O4PS2	[M+H] ⁺	321.03786	135.0433	12.77	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Phosalone	C12H15ClNO4PS2	[M+H] ⁺	367.99414	182.0003	13.25	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Phosmet	C11H12NO4PS2	[M+H] ⁺	318.00181	160.0395	10.96	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Phoxim	C12H15N2O3PS	[M+H] ⁺	299.06138	77.0388	13.17	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Pirimicarb	C11H18N4O2	[M+H] ⁺	239.15025	72.0437	7.92	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Pirimicarb, desmethyl-	C10H16N4O2	[M+H] ⁺	225.1346	72.0439	5.15	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Pirimiphos-methyl	C11H20N3O3PS	[M+H] ⁺	306.10358	164.1178	13.17	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Prochloraz	C15H16Cl3N3O2	[M+H] ⁺	376.03809	308.0015	12.97	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)

Compound name	Formula	Adduct	Precursor ion m/z	Fragment ion m/z	Retention time (min)	Experiment index
Profenofos	C11H15BrClO3PS	[M+H] ⁺	372.94242	302.8638	13.93	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Propamocarb	C9H20N2O2	[M+H] ⁺	189.15975	102.0548	1.94	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Propaquizafop	C22H22ClN3O5	[M+H] ⁺	444.13207	100.0755	13.89	6 +TOF MSMS [439 - 525] (50 - 950)
Propargite	C19H26O4S	[M+NH4] ⁺	368.18901	175.1117	14.61	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Propiconazole	C15H17Cl2N3O2	[M+H] ⁺	342.07706	158.9768	12.96	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Propoxur	C11H15NO3	[M+H] ⁺	210.11247	111.0432	9.1	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Propyzamide	C12H11Cl2NO	[M+H] ⁺	256.02905	172.9558	11.83	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Proquinazid	C14H17IN2O2	[M+H] ⁺	373.04075	288.9467	14.65	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Pymetrozine	C10H11N5O	[M+H] ⁺	218.10364	105.0449	1.36	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Pyraclostrobin	C19H18ClN3O4	[M+H] ⁺	388.10586	163.0624	13	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Pyridaben	C19H25ClN2OS	[M+H] ⁺	365.14489	147.116	15.05	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Pyridate	C19H23ClN2O2S	[M+H] ⁺	379.12415	207.0316	15.3	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Pyrimethanil	C12H13N3	[M+H] ⁺	200.11822	107.0605	10.58	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Pyriproxyfen	C20H19NO3	[M+H] ⁺	322.14377	96.0445	14.09	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Quinoclamine	C10H6ClNO2	[M+H] ⁺	208.01598	105.0334	8.27	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Quinoxifen	C15H8Cl2FNO	[M+H] ⁺	308.00397	196.9793	14.21	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Rotenone	C23H22O6	[M+H] ⁺	395.14891	213.0911	12.37	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Spinosyn A	C41H65NO10	[M+H] ⁺	732.46812	142.1224	13.07	9 +TOF MSMS [694 - 780] (50 - 950)
Spinosyn D	C42H67NO10	[M+H] ⁺	746.48377	142.1222	13.39	9 +TOF MSMS [694 - 780] (50 - 950)
Spirodiclofen	C21H24Cl2O4	[M+H] ⁺	411.11244	313.0391	14.92	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Spiromesifen	C23H30O4	[M+H] ⁺	371.22169	273.149	14.71	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Spirotetramat	C21H27NO5	[M+H] ⁺	374.1962	216.1017	12.22	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Spiroxamine	C18H35NO2	[M+H] ⁺	298.27406	144.1377	11.47	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Tebuconazole	C16H22ClN3O	[M+H] ⁺	308.15242	125.0151	12.95	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Tebufenozide	C22H28N2O2	[M+H] ⁺	353.22235	133.0645	12.84	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Tebufenpyrad	C18H24ClN3O	[M+H] ⁺	334.16807	145.0527	14.08	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)

Compound name	Formula	Adduct	Precursor ion m/z	Fragment ion m/z	Retention time (min)	Experiment index
Terbutylazine	C9H16ClN5	[M+H] ⁺	230.1167	174.0535	11.58	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Tetraconazole	C13H11Cl2F4N3O	[M+H] ⁺	372.02881	158.9761	12.45	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Thiabendazole	C10H7N3S	[M+H] ⁺	202.04334	175.0327	4.33	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Thiacloprid	C10H9ClN4S	[M+H] ⁺	253.03092	126.0098	7.09	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Thiamethoxam	C8H10ClN5O3S	[M+H] ⁺	292.02656	181.0556	3.67	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Thiobencarb	C12H16ClNOS	[M+H] ⁺	258.07139	125.0149	13.32	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Tolclofos-methyl	C9H11Cl2O3PS	[M+H] ⁺	300.96163	174.9715	13.1	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Triazophos	C12H16N3O3PS	[M+H] ⁺	314.07228	162.0653	12.05	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Trichlorfon	C4H8Cl3O4P	[M+H] ⁺	256.92986	109.0048	6.14	3 +TOF MSMS [184 - 270] (50 - 950)
Trifloxystrobin	C20H19F3N2O4	[M+H] ⁺	409.13697	186.0515	13.68	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Triflumuron	C15H10ClF3N2O3	[M+H] ⁺	359.04048	156.0209	13.21	5 +TOF MSMS [354 - 440] (50 - 950)
Triticonazole	C17H20ClN3O	[M+H] ⁺	318.13677	70.0407	12.28	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)
Zoxamide	C14H16Cl3NO2	[M+H] ⁺	336.03194	186.9709	13.12	4 +TOF MSMS [269 - 355] (50 - 950)